

Review Article

A Review on the Physicochemical and Biological Properties of Benzoxazole and Thiazole Derivatives

Nitika*, Dr. Chinu Kumari, Dr. Abhishek Soni, Bhopesh Kumar, Yushmita Thakur, Riya Verma, Saurabh Rana

School of Pharmacy, Abhilashi University, Chailchowk, Mandi, Himachal Pradesh, India 175028

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 13 May 2026

Keywords:

Benzoxazole, Thiazole, Heterocyclic scaffolds, Physicochemical properties, Structural adaptability, Drug development, biological activity.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20151500

ABSTRACT

Benzoxazole and thiazole derivatives have emerged as important heterocyclic scaffolds in medicinal chemistry due to their diverse physicochemical characteristics and broad pharmacological potential. Their unique ring structures contribute to favorable physical properties that enhance membrane permeability, stability, planarity, and moderate hydrogen-bonding capacity. Both thiazole and benzoxazole cores possess a high degree of structural adaptability, which allows significant substitution and functional modification to maximize biological activity. These compounds are promising candidates for drug development, as they exhibit important therapeutic properties such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, anticancer, antitubercular, and antiviral activities. This review highlights the fundamental physical and chemical properties of benzoxazole and thiazole derivatives, correlates these characteristics with their biological behavior, and summarizes recent advancements in their medicinal applications and therapeutic potential. Understanding the relationship between their structural features and pharmacological effects may support the rational development of new and novel, effective, and safer therapeutic agents based on these heterocyclic frameworks.

INTRODUCTION

Heterocyclic compounds play a vital role in pharmaceutical research due to their unique structural diversity and broad spectrum of biological activities. Among these, benzoxazole and thiazole derivatives have emerged as important scaffolds in medicinal chemistry,

exhibiting notable chemical, physical, and medicinal properties. Through structural modifications and substitution patterns, the benzoxazole core—a fused benzene and oxazole ring—contributes to diverse pharmacological actions, including antibacterial, antifungal,

***Corresponding Author:** Riya Verma

Address: School of Pharmacy, Abhilashi University, Chailchowk, Mandi, Himachal Pradesh, India 175028

Email ✉: guptanitika171@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and central nervous system activities.^[1]

BENZOXAZOLE

Benzoxazole- First created in 1947, oxazole is an unsaturated five-membered heterocycle with oxygen (O) and nitrogen (N) heteroatoms at positions 1 and 3, separated by a carbon (C) atom (Fig. 1a).^[2] A fused bicyclic aromatic heterocycle with a 1,3-oxazole ring structure and benzene is called benzoxazole (Fig. 1b). The benzene ring is planar and composed of six carbon atoms, while the 1,3-oxazole ring contains one atom each of oxygen (O) and nitrogen (N). The fusion of these rings creates a bridging structure, resulting in a fused bicyclic system with aromatic

properties.^[3,4] The composition of the benzoxazole scaffold's structure enables effective communication with biological targets. Planar benzene rings can produce π -cation or π - π stacking interactions. engagement with the host molecule, whereas the 1-oxygen and the oxazole moiety's third nitrogen form a hydrogen bond. Therefore, non-covalent interactions occur between acceptors. Additionally, the lipophilic properties of benzoxazoles enable interactions with hydrophobic target proteins.^[5] Benzoxazoles are also considered the bio isosteres of guanine and adenine, two nucleic bases. Benzoxazoles and biopolymers can interact favorably in living systems due to their structural similarity. The wide range of biological activity seen in them could also be attributed to this.^[6]

[a] 1,3-oxazole

[b] benzo [d] oxazole

Fig 1. Structural formulae of [a] oxazole and [b] benzo[d] oxazole

Chemistry and Structural Features of Benzoxazole

Benzoxazole is a fused heterocyclic compound made of a benzene ring + oxazole ring. It contains two heteroatoms: Nitrogen (N) and Oxygen (O). The molecule is stable, planar, and suitable for biological interactions because these atoms provide an impact on electron distribution.

Ring Structure and Aromaticity of Benzoxazole:

Benzoxazole is aromatic, meaning it follows the planar cyclic conjugation rule (π -electrons).

- The conjugation of a fused ring system is continuous.

- It shows high stability due to resonance.
- Aromaticity improves π - π stacking and enzyme/receptor interaction.^[7]

Substitution Pattern and Reactivity of Benzoxazole

The electron distribution and aromatic structure of benzoxazole have a major impact on its substitution pattern and reactivity. Due to their higher electron density and higher reactivity compared with electrophiles, the C-5 and C-7 positions of the benzene ring are usually the sites of electrophilic substitution processes. On the other hand, because electronegative nitrogen and oxygen atoms produce an electron-deficient core at the C-2 position of the oxazole ring, it is more exposed to nucleophilic substitution. Due to its

unique electrophilic and nucleophilic reactivity, benzoxazole is a dynamic scaffold for drug design and chemical modification.^[8]

Functionalization at Different Positions:

Adding chemical groups to improve properties is commonly referred to as functionalization:

- The most important position for pharmacological activity is C-2.
- C-5 and C-6 positions → Commonly modified

In medicinal chemistry, such modifications enhance stability, improve binding, and enhance biological activity.^[9]

2. Reaction with Aldehydes:

2-Arylbenzoxazoles were produced directly from substituted 2-aminophenols and aldehydes in xylene with activated carbon in an oxygenated environment. For the production of 2-arylbenzoxazole compounds of potential medicinal interest, a straightforward and effective

3. Reaction with alcohols:

2-substituted benzoxazole is produced in good yield when O-amino phenol and alcohol react in

4. Reaction with ester:

Synthesis of Benzoxazoles

1. Reaction with Acids:

When amino phenols are heated to high temperatures with a dehydrating agent (polyphosphoric acid, phosphorus pentoxide, methanesulfonic acid, H₃BO₃), they can cyclize to benzoxazoles in the presence of carboxylic acids.^[7] The corresponding 2-alkyl or 2-arylbenzoxazoles are formed when equimolar concentrations of 2-aminophenols and alkyl or arylcarboxylic acids are heated to temperatures between 140 and 220°C.^[10]

technique has been designed. The process entails the reaction of 2-aminophenol with substituted aromatic aldehydes in acetonitrile, with anhydrous bismuth trichloride acting as a catalyst. Some appealing aspects of this technology include the use of environmentally benign bismuth trichloride, generally gentle reaction conditions, and moderate to good product yield.^[11]

the presence of a catalytic quantity of a ruthenium complex.^[12]

Trialkyl Ortho ester, o-aminophenol, o-phenylenediamine, or 2-amino-3-

hydroxypyridine, and silica sulfuric acid were added together and stirred for the proper amount of time at either room temperature or 85°C. TLC (eluent: n-hexane: ethyl acetate,2:1) was used to monitor the reaction's progress. The mixture was filtered once the reaction was finished and diluted

with 10 cc of CHCl₃. After being cleaned with CHCl₃, the solid material was dried at 60° C. The residue was purified by either column chromatography on neutral alumina or recrystallization in n-hexane after the filtrate was evaporated.^[13]

THIAZOLE

It was first described by Hantzsch and Weber in 1887.^[14] The thiazole ring is a naturally occurring substance that is predominantly found in marine and microbial sources. Natural compounds that include peptides^[15], vitamins (such as thiamine), alkaloids, epothilone, and chlorophyll^[16,17]. Thiazoles have relatively low toxicity toward mammals. It has shown various biological activities like antioxidant, analgesic, antibacterial, anticancer, anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and antimalarial.^[18,19,20] It has also shown hypnotic,^[21] diuretic and neuroprotective activities.^[22,23] The thiazole ring, characterized by a five-membered heterocycle containing nitrogen and sulfur, serves as a key structural motif in numerous bioactive compounds. Its physicochemical features, such as the presence of heteroatoms and aromaticity, significantly influence pharmacokinetic behavior and molecular interactions with biological targets.^[24]

Fig 2. Structure of thiazole

Chemistry and Structural Features of Thiazole:

Thiazole is a five-membered heterocyclic compound containing one nitrogen and one sulfur atom in its ring. Due to conjugation, structure is stable and flattened. Thiazole contains unique electronic properties due to the presence of sulfur and nitrogen atoms, making it important in medicinal chemistry and drug development.^[25]

Ring Structure and Aromaticity: Thiazole is an aromatic compound that follows Huckel's rule ($4n + 2 \pi$ electrons), having a total of 6 π -electrons in the ring. Sulfur helps in electron delocalization, while nitrogen's lone pair helps the aromatic system. Its aromaticity influences its chemical behavior and provides it stability.^[26]

Substitution Pattern and Reactivity of Thiazole: C-5 position in thiazole has a higher electron density, electrophilic substitution usually occurs here. Since nitrogen and sulfur atoms exhibit an electron-withdrawing property, the C-2 position is more reactive to nucleophilic substitution. Thiazole is versatile for chemical modifications because it shows both electrophilic and nucleophilic reactivity.^[27]

Functionalization at Different Positions of Thiazole: Thiazole can be easily modified at specific position by using a number of methods. Because the C-5 position is more reactive toward electrophiles, methods including nitration, halogenation, and sulfonation are usually used

here. Different groups are added at the C-2 position through coupling reactions like Suzuki, Heck, as well as nucleophilic substitution. Selective substitution is further helped by

metalation methods such as lithiation. These reactions make it easy to prepare a variety of useful thiazole derivatives.^[28]

Fig3. Resonance of the thiazole ring

It can successfully interact with biological targets due to its adaptability, particularly through van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonds that connect molecules with amino acid residues in the receptor protein.^[30] This structure has both an electron-donating group ($-S-$) and an electron-withdrawing group ($-C = N-$). The system stability and reactivity patterns are directly influenced by the electronic distribution within the ring, which is strengthened by the electronegativity of nitrogen and the involvement of sulfur's orbitals. While nucleophiles often target the C-2 position, electrophilic substitution processes preferentially take place at the C-5 and C-4 Position.^[29-31] In addition, the type of substituents linked to the ring can alter the thiazole's activity profile. The structure's basicity and nucleophilicity are increased by electron-donating groups, enhancing its use as a bioactive scaffold in the development of new drugs.^[29]

A number of compounds, like thioamides, thiourea, ammonium thiocarbamate or Di thiocarbamate, and their derivatives, may act as nucleophilic reagents in this reaction. In 1887, Hantzsch created the basic thiazole nucleus.^[32] This synthesis approach involves cyclization and condensation of haloketones with thioamide, and it is considered the most widely popular process for the synthesis of thiazole moiety.^[33]

Synthesis from α -halo carbonyl compounds (Hantzsch's synthesis)

- 1. Reactions with thioamides:** Several thiazoles with alkyl, aryl, arylalkyl, or heteroaryl functional groups at positions 2, 4, or 5 were produced through an interaction with thioamides and various α -halo carbonyl compounds. (Synthesis of 2-, 4-, 5-trisubstituted thiazole.)^[34]

- 2. Reactions with N-substituted thiourea:** Halo carbonyl compounds reacted with N-substituted thiourea compounds to produce

monosubstituted or disubstituted aminothiazoles.^[35] (Synthesis of substituted aminothiazoles.)

3. Reaction with esters of Thio carbamic acid:
2-hydroxythiazole derivatives were produced by condensing α -halo carbonyl compounds

with thiocarbamates.^[36] (Synthesis of 2-hydroxythiazole derivatives.)

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of benzoxazole and Thiazole ^[37,38,39,40,41]

Property	Benzoxazole	Thiazole
Chemical Formula	C ₇ H ₅ NO	C ₃ H ₃ NS
Molecular Weight	119.12 g/mol	85.12 g/mol
Structure Type	Fused benzene-oxazole ring	Five-membered heterocycle with N and S
Physical State (at RT)	Colorless to pale yellow Solid	Colorless to pale-yellow liquid
Appearance	White to light yellow solid	Pale yellow liquid
Melting Point	27–30°C	–20 to –5°C
Boiling Point	280–300°C	116–118°C
Density	1.20 g/cm ³	1.10 g/cm ³
Aromaticity	Aromatic fused ring	Aromatic heterocycle
Planarity	planar and rigid	Planar
Solubility in Water	Very low / practically insoluble	Miscible / moderately soluble
Solubility in Organic Solvents	Soluble in ethanol, chloroform, benzene, acetone, DMSO	Soluble in ethanol, ether, chloroform, benzene
Polarity / Dipole Moment	Moderate (due to oxygen and nitrogen)	Moderate (due to sulfur and nitrogen)
Log P (Approx.)	1.5–2.5	0.4–1.0
Permeability	higher permeability	moderate permeability
Odor	Mild aromatic	Pyridine-like
Aromatic Electron System	Strong π -electron delocalization	π -electron delocalization
Basicity	Very weak base (sp ² hybridization)	Weak base (sp ² hybridization)

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF BENZOXAZOLE DERIVATIVES ^[42]

Fig 4. Medicinal properties of benzoxazole

1. Anticancer Activity-

Balasubrahmanian N *et al.* (2020) reported the synthesis of 2-(2-((benzoxazol-2-ylthio) methyl)-1H-benzimidazol-1-yl) acetyl hydrazide derivatives. The human colorectal carcinoma [HCT116 (ATCC (American Type Culture Collection) CCL247)] cancer cell line was used in the 2- (3-diethyl-amino-6-diethylazaniumylidene-

xanthen 9-yl)-5-sulfobenzene-sulfonate (SRB) assay to evaluate the anticancer activity of the synthesized derivatives. Previously, Balasubrahmanian reported the synthesis of benzoxazole derivatives. The human colorectal cancer cell line HCT 116 (ATCC CCL-247) was used to assess the antiproliferative characteristics of the benzazole derivatives. The standard drug is 5-fluorouracil (IC₅₀=12.2 μM).^[43]

2. Antioxidant Activity-

Using the amount of copper as an oxidizing agent, the authors *et al.* (2025) synthesized 2(3H)-benzoxazolone derivatives and evaluated their in-vitro antioxidant activity at a dose of 10 μM to stop human LDL copper-induced oxidation. Compound 3 demonstrated more antioxidant activity and inhibited the beginning and growth of copper-mediated LDL oxidation in a dose- and time-dependent manner.^[44]

3. Anti-inflammatory Activity-

The inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX) is largely responsible for the therapeutic and adverse effects of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs), which are a standard in the treatment of

inflammation.^[45] One of the biggest challenges in the design and synthesis of these medications has been isolating the therapeutic effects from the negative effects. The identification of a second isoform of COX, COX-2, has led to new research based on the hypothesis that the constitutive isoform COX-1 produces physiological prostaglandins, whereas the inducible isoform COX-2 produces pathological prostaglandins.^[46] FT-IR, ¹H NMR, MS, and elemental analysis were used to characterize a series of N-(acridin-9-yl)-4-(benzo[d]imidazol/oxazol-2-yl) benzamides who were produced by combining 9-amino acridine derivatives with benzoxazole derivatives. It was discovered that these chemical compounds had noticeable anti-inflammatory properties.^[47]

4. Anticonvulsant Activity

PTZ (Pentylenetetrazol) -induced convulsions in albino mice were used to test their in vivo anticonvulsant efficacy of 2-mercapto benzoxazole and 2-mercapto benzimidazole. A large number of the substances indicated the capacity to prevent convulsions produced by the chemical pentylenetetrazol. If compared to a normal medication, several molecules showed the highest level of action. Biologically active Benzoxazole.^[48]

The authors Sener E. *et al.* (2010) synthesized derivatives of 5-amino-2-(p-substituted-phenyl)

5. Antimicrobial Activity

Elnima EI *et al.* (2017) examined the antifungal and antimicrobial properties of six benzimidazole and benzoxazole derivatives in vitro. They have been compared to reference strains and 59 clinical isolates. Out of the six compounds, only two (both benzoxazoles) exhibited any action. Following treatment with these medications, all common strains—including fungus and gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria—showed significant growth reduction. Fifty-nine clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* were tested for their susceptibility to the two drugs. The most susceptible were the *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates. Although compound (6) showed slightly more activity than compound (7), both drugs were equally effective against every isolate. Either of its respective minimal the bacterium *S. aureus* was 90% inhibited at inhibitory doses of 25 and 50 µg/ml. The gram-negative bacteria needed just 200 µg/ml of inhibitory concentration to produce a comparable level of inhibition because they were immune against both compounds.^[49]

benzoxazole. They were made by heating 2, 4-diaminophenol with the appropriate carboxylic

acids in the presence of polyphosphoric acid. 2-substituted benzoxazoles have been extensively investigated since position 5 predominates in terms of activity intensity, leading to the conclusion that biological activity is determined by this position. Benzoxazoprofen and zoxazolamin are examples of benzoxazole compounds that are substituted at positions two and five.^[50]

5-Amino-2-(p-Substituted-Phenyl) Benzoxazole Derivatives

R	Acid used as starting compound
H	Benzoic acid
C ₂ H ₅	p-Ethyl benzoic acid
Br	p-Bromo benzoic acid
F	p-Fluorobenzoic acid
N(CH ₃) ₃	p-Dimethylaminobenzoic acid
NO ₂	p-Nitrobenzoic acid

6. Antifungal Activity-

1. New antifungal drugs with a 1,3-benzoxazole-4-carbonitrile skeleton and a novel mode of action that inhibits the synthesis of β -1,6-glucan, which is known to be important for the cellular growth and proliferation of *Candida* spp.¹¹—were discovered, according to Jun-Ichi Kuroyanagi *et al.* (2007) Compound (9) showed strong antifungal activity against *Candida* spp. among those 1,3-benzoxazole analogs.^[51]

2. Beom Joon Kim *et al.* (2010) developed and synthesized benzoxazole amides and assessed their antifungal efficacy against *Malassezia furfur* based on the chemical structure of Malassezin-reported benzoxazole derivatives. Twelve amides of benzoxazole derivatives (4a-h and 8a-d) were prepared with substitution shown in Table 2 and 3. Compounds 4a, 8b, 8c and 8d showed antifungal activity with clear zone of 15, 8, 10 and 12 mm, respectively.^[52]

Table 2. Different substituted compounds 4(a-h).

Compound	R1	R2	R3
4a	H	H	H
4b	H	Cl	H
4c	H	NO ₂	H
4d	H	OCH ₃	H
4e	H	H	CH ₃
4f	CH ₃	H	H
4g	H	COOH	H
4h	H	CF ₃	H

Table 3. Different substituted compounds 8 (a-d).

Compound	R1	R2	R3
8a	H	C ₃ H ₆ NS ₂	H
8b	Cl	H	NO ₂
8c	H	H	CH ₃
8d	H	H	OCH ₃

7. Analgesic Activity-

Praveen *et al.* (2013) created a benzoxazole derivative using a cyclocondensation reaction and used the tail immersion method to test its analgesic

properties. According to the study's findings, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 had the lowest analgesic potency (50.6%, 50.9%, 51.3%, 51.3%, and 50%). While compounds 17, 18, and 19 showed greater analgesic potency (73.5%, 76.4%, and 74%),

compounds 20 and 21 showed intermediate analgesic potential (54.5% and 59.6%, respectively). In this experiment, pentazocine served as a positive control.^[53]

8. Antitubercular Activity-

1. A series of 2-benzylsulfanyl derivatives of benzoxazole were synthesized by Klimesova V *et al.* (2012) and their antimycobacterial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, nontuberculous mycobacteria, and multidrug-resistant *M. tuberculosis* was assessed in vitro. Benzoxazole's dinitrobenzylsulfanyl derivative is one of the most promising synthesized small-molecule antimycobacterial.^[54]

2. Vinsova Jarmila *et al.* synthesized 3, 5-di-tert-butyl-1, 2-benzoquinone, which reacts with amino acids and dipeptides containing N-terminal glycine to produce a series of lipophilic 2-substituted 5, 7-di-tertbutylbenzoxazoles. Oxidative deamination occurs in dipeptides with different N-terminal amino acids. 5,7-Di-tert-butylbenzoxazoles (23) shown efficacy against certain nontuberculous strains of *Mycobacterium*

Tuberculosis, while isoniazid has not showed any effect.^[55]

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF THIAZOLE DERIVATIVES

1. Anti-inflammatory Activity-

The anti-inflammatory and lipoxigenase and cyclooxygenase inhibitory properties of a number of adamantane derivatives of thiazolyl-N-substituted amides were investigated. (24) of the substances that were evaluated had strong activity.^[56]

2. Anticonvulsant Activity-

4-fluoro-N-[4-[6-(isopropyl amino)-pyrimidin-4-yl]thiazol-2-yl] N-methyl benzamide (25) is a strong mGluR1 antagonist that could be used as a PET tracer to better understand how mGluR1 functions in humans. A series of N4-(naphtha[1,2-d]thiazol-2-yl) semi carbazide (26) was developed and synthesized by Azam.^[57] and assessed for their neurotoxicity and anticonvulsant properties. A molecule with p-methoxyphenyl (27) substitution at C-2 of the thiazolidinone ring was discovered to be beneficial for activity in a series of thiazolidinonyl 2-oxo/Thio barbituric acid derivatives and shown to have more potent anticonvulsant activity compared to the standard drug sodium phenytoin.^[58]

3. Antitubercular Activity-

Due to poverty and the HIV/AIDS pandemic, Mycobacterium tuberculosis infections are becoming more common these days. Therefore, the primary issues are the efficacy of traditional

antitubercular medications and the development of multidrug-resistant strains of M. tuberculosis.^[56] Certain compounds containing thiazoles showed promising antitubercular effects among antitubercular agents. A number of 2-(2-hydrazinyl) thiazole derivatives were created and

tested against Mycobacterium tuberculosis in a study by Makam, PhD, and colleagues. Ethyl-4-methyl-2-[(E)-2-[1-(pyridin-2-yl) ethylidene] hydrazinyl] -1,3-Thiazole-5-carboxylate (28) was one of the produced compounds that showed significant inhibitory efficacy against M. tuberculosis.^[57]

4. Antiviral Agents-

Viral infection is one of the most common and fatal diseases, taking several lives annually. There is an urgent need to discover more powerful and efficient agents, even with recent developments in the field of antiviral medications. Many thiazole-based compounds were produced and assessed in this field; some of these are reported below. Mayhoub et al. produced and evaluated a novel generation of methyl 4-dibromomethyl 2-(4-chlorophenyl) (29), the most effective derivative among the primary compounds, against the yellow fever virus using a cell-based assay.^[59]

5. Anticancer activity-

Examined the synthesis and activity of many 4-thiazolyl-substituted analogs of new

pyrrolocarbazole as poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase-1 (PARP-1) inhibitors. (30) of these substances have been shown to be stronger than others.^[60]

For the purpose of isolating aryl-substituted benzothiazoles, the researchers S *et al.* (2014) refluxed aminophenol's with substituted benzoic acid in the presence of polyphosphoric acid (31) at a higher temperature. They subsequently evaluated these compounds as treatments against human cervical cancer cell lines.^[61]

The synthesis of 2-(5-((5-(4-chloro-phenyl) furan-2-yl) methylene)-4-oxo-2-thioxothiazolidin-3-yl) acetic acid derivatives and an evaluation of their cytotoxic activities have been reported by Chandrappa *et al.* (2007), Compounds with electron-donating groups at the C-terminal of the phenyl ring were found to improve activity by inducing cell death, while compounds with electron-withdrawing groups (CN, F, and CF₃) showed lower activity. Due to its electron-donating methoxy group, compound (31) was found to be the most potent since it showed the greatest cytotoxicity. In addition, compound (32) shows chromosomal DNA fragmentation at 50 μM.^[62]

6. Antifungal activity-

By synthesizing 4-bromoacetyl-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline with thiourea, Mohamed Salah K. Youssef *et al.* (2009) synthesized a series of 4-(2-Aminothiazol-4-yl)-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline. They evaluated the antibacterial efficacy of these substances against various fungal strains, including *Aspergillus flavus*, *Candida albicans*, *Geotrichum candidum*, and *Scopulariopsis brevicaulis*. *Aspergillus rubrum* and *Aspergillus niger*. 3- (4,5-dihydro -3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4- [3,2-a] yl)-6H-thiazolo with low inhibitory concentrations (MIC=5-50 mg/cm³), pyrimidine-5,7-dione (33) shows a broad range of antifungal activity but a small spectrum of antibacterial activity.^[63]

Applying the serial plate dilution method 24, thiazole derivatives have been evaluated for their antifungal activity against *Trichophyton* and *Geotrichum* (recultured) in DMSO. The diameter of the fungal colonies was used to measure the antifungal activity. At concentrations of 20 mg/ml and 25 mg/ml, compound (34) proved to be the most effective against *Trichophyton* and *Geotrichum*.

7. Antitumor activity-

A number of new ethyl 2-substituted aminothiazole-4-carboxylate analogs have been synthesized, and the National Cancer Institute (NCI) tested the compounds for their potential anticancer activity against 60 human tumor cell lines in vitro. 2-[3-(diethylamino)-prop ethyl-thiazole-4-carboxylate (35) shows outstanding activity against the

leukemia cell line RPMI-8226 with a GI value of 0.08 μ M and a broad-spectrum activity against each tumor cell line used, with a GI (MG-MID) value of 38.3 μ M.^[64]

8. Antimicrobial activity-

Six 3-methyl -1-[(5-substituted-1H-indol-2-yl) carbonyl] -4- {[4-(substitutedthiazol-2-yl) iminoethyl] phenyl] hydrazono} Derivatives of 2-pyrazolin-5-one were created using both traditional and microwave methods. The antimicrobial capacity of the resulting compounds has been evaluated against three fungal strains and six bacterial strains. While most of the other compounds displayed diverse antibacterial activity, compound (36) showed a wide range of

activity against bacteria, and compound (37) has shown excellent antimicrobial activity.^[65]

STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP OF BENZOXAZOLE AND THIAZOLE

Fig 5. Numbering and SAR- relevant substitution position of benzoxazole scaffold

Fig 6. Numbering and SAR- relevant substitution position of thiazole scaffold

The C-2 position in benzoxazole is the main substitution site and is important for controlling biological activity. The molecule's general physicochemical properties, steric effects, and electronic characteristics are able to be modified via substitutions at the C-5 and C-6 positions. The C-2 position acts as the main pharmacophoric site in thiazole derivatives, but modifications at the C-4 and C-5 positions influence molecular stability, biological activity, and selectivity. Designing new derivatives with better therapeutic qualities needs an understanding of these substitution patterns.^[66,67]

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Benzoxazole and thiazole derivatives are important heterocyclic compounds with strong potential in medicinal chemistry. Their favorable physical and chemical properties, along with their wide range of biological activities, make them useful structures for developing new drugs. However, many aspects of these compounds are still underexplored. Continued research, synthesis of new derivatives, and detailed SAR studies are needed to better understand their therapeutic value and to design safer and more effective medicines in the future.

Future research on benzoxazole and thiazole derivatives rather than depending only on in vitro potency, there should be a greater focus on integrated optimization of scaffold behavior under

physiological conditions. Physicochemical parameters and ADME features have not been systematically correlated with in vivo performance for these scaffolds despite a great deal of computational and synthetic study. The exploration of scaffold-driven multi-target effects and disease-context-dependent activity remains inadequately investigated. Strengthening mechanism-based in vivo validation and translational studies will be important in developing benzoxazole and thiazole derivatives toward clinically promising drug candidates.

REFERENCES

1. Kamal U, Javed NM, Arun K. Biological potential of benzoxazole derivatives: an updated review. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2020;13(8):28–41. doi:10.22159/ajpcr.2020.v13i8.37958.
2. Shainda L, Anup SK, Hefazat SH. Advances in the synthetic strategies of benzoxazoles using 2-aminophenol as a precursor: an up-to-date review. *Indo Am J Pharm Res.* 2013;3:8550–8562.
3. Aggarwal N, Kaur A, Anand K, Kumar H, Wakode SR. Advances in the synthetic strategies of benzoxazoles using 2-aminophenol as a precursor: an up-to-date review. *Int J Pharm Sci.* 2017; 2(2):1–5.
4. Paliwal R, Bhargava S. Advances in the synthetic strategies of benzoxazoles using 2-aminophenol as a precursor: an up-to-date review. *Int J Adv Res Pharm Bio Sci.* 2014;4(1):B1.
5. Demmer CS, Bunch L. Benzoxazoles and oxazolopyridines in medicinal chemistry studies. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2015; 97:778–785. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2014.11.064.
6. Khai X, Yoon K. A patent review on the current developments of benzoxazoles in drug discovery. *ChemMedChem.* 2021; 16:1–27. doi:10.1002/cmdc.202100370.
7. A. R. Katritzky, C. W. Rees, and E. F. V. Scriven, “Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry II: A Review of the Literature 1982–1995,” 4 (1996): 1–126.
8. F. A. Carey and R. J. Sundberg, “Advanced Organic Chemistry Part A: Structure and Mechanisms,” Springer 5 (2007): 580–590.
9. R. S. Keri, A. Hiremath ad, S. Budagumpi, and B. M. Nagaraja, “Benzoxazole Derivatives: Comprehensive Review on Current Developments in Medicinal Chemistry,” *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 78 (2014): 340–374.
10. Paliwal R, Bhargava S. A review on synthesis and various reactions of benzoxazole. *Int J Adv Res Pharm Bio Sci.* 2014;4(1):1–6. ISSN: 2277-6222.
11. Ramanatham Vinod Kumar. Synthetic Strategies towards Benzoxazole Ring System: A Review, *Asian Journal of Chemistry.* 2004; 16(3-4):1241-1260.
12. Aggarwal N, Kaur A, Anand K, Kumar H, Wakode SR. Biologically active Benzoxazole: A comprehensive review. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.* 2017;2(2):1-5.
13. Potasman MH, Bready J, Coxon A, Dipetro L, Deorr N. Design synthesis and evaluation of orally active benzimidazole and benzoxazoles as vascular endothelial growth factor-2 receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitors. *J Med Chem.* 2007; 50:4351-73.
14. Hantzsch, A.; Weber, J. Ueber verbindungen des thiazole (pyridins der thiophen Reihe). *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1887, 20(2), 3118-3132.
15. Videnov G, Kaiser D, Kempter C, Jung G. Synthesis of naturally occurring, conformationally restricted oxazole- and thiazole-containing di- and tripeptide mimetics. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl.* 1996; 35:1503–1506. doi:10.1002/anie.199615031.

16. Utkina NK, Sagitol D, a new thiazole-containing pyridoacridine alkaloid from a Vietnamese ascidian. *Nat Prod Commun.* 2015;10(9):1547–1548. doi:10.1177/1934578X1501000915. PMID:26594755.
17. Molnár I, Schupp T, Ono M, Zirkle R, Milnamow M, Nowak-Thompson B, et al. The biosynthetic gene cluster for the microtubule-stabilizing agents epothilones A and B from *Sorangium cellulosum* So ce90. *Chem Biol.* 2000;7(2):97–109. doi:10.1016/S1074-5521(00)00075-2. PMID:10662695.
18. T, Ono M, Zirkle R, Milnamow M, Nowak-Thompson B, et al. The biosynthetic gene cluster for the microtubule-stabilizing agents epothilones A and B from *Sorangium cellulosum* So ce90. *Chem Biol.* 2000;7(2):97–109. doi:10.1016/S1074-5521(00)00075-2. PMID:10662695.
19. Gurupadayya BM, Gopal M, Padmashali B, Manohara YN. Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of azetidino-2-ones and thiazolidino-4-ones encompassing benzothiazole. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2008;70(5):572–577. doi:10.4103/0250-474X.45393. PMID:21394251.
20. Laczkowski KZ, Biernasiuk A, Baranowska-Laczkowska A, Misiura K, Malm A, Plech T, Paneth A. Synthesis, antibacterial activity, interaction with nucleobase and molecular docking studies of 4-formylbenzoic acid-based thiazoles. *Med Chem.* 2016;12(6):553–562. doi:10.2174/1573406412666160201121310. PMID:26833073.
21. Muhammad ZA, Masaret GS, Amin MM, Abdallah MA, Farghaly TA. Anti-inflammatory, analgesic and anti-ulcerogenic activities of novel bis-thiadiazoles, bis-thiazoles and bisformazanes. *Med Chem.* 2017;13(3):226–238. doi:10.2174/1573406412666160920091146. PMID:27659119.
22. Ergenç N, Çapan G, Günay NS, Özkirimli S, Güngör M, Özbey S, Kendi E. Synthesis and hypnotic activity of new 4-thiazolidinone and 2-thioxo-4,5-imidazolidinedione derivatives. *Arch Pharm (Weinheim).* 1999;332(10):343–347. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1521-4184(199910)332:10<343: AID-ARDP343>3.0.CO;2-0. PMID:10575366.
23. Andreani A, Rambaldi M, Mascellani G, Rugarli P. Synthesis and diuretic activity of imidazol[2,1-b] thiazole acetohydrazone. *Eur J Med Chem.* 1987;22(1):19–22. doi:10.1016/0223-5234(87)90169-3.
24. Koufaki M, Kiziridi C, Nikoloudaki F, Alexis MN. Design and synthesis of 1,2-dithiolane derivatives and evaluation of their neuroprotective activity. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett.* 2007;17(15):4223–4227. doi:10.1016/j.bmcl.2007.05.036. PMID:17531485.
25. Kashyap SJ, Garg VK, Sharma PK, Kumar N, Gupta JK. Thiazoles: having diverse biological activities. *Med Chem Res.* 2012;21(8):2123–2132.
26. Chhabria MT, Patel S, Modi P, Brahm kshatriya PS. Thiazole: a review on chemistry, synthesis and therapeutic importance. *Curr Top Med Chem.* 2016;16(26):2841–2862.
27. Mishra R, Sharma PK, Verma PK, Tomer I. Recent advances in the synthesis and pharmacological activity of thiazole derivatives: a review. *J Enzyme Inhib Med Chem.* 2017;32(1):1–18.
28. Singh GS, Desta ZY. Isothiazole, thiazole, and their derivatives: synthesis and applications in medicinal chemistry. *Chem Rev.* 2012;112(11):6104–6155.
29. Chhabria MT, Patel S, Modi P, Brahm kshatriya PS. Thiazole: a review on chemistry,

- synthesis and therapeutic importance of its derivatives. *Curr Top Med Chem.* 2016;16(26):2841–2862. doi:10.2174/1568026616666160506130731.
30. S. Parit, A. Manchare, S. Ghodse, and N. Hatvate, “Comparative Review on Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Catalyzed Synthesis of 1,3-Thiazole,” *Synthetic Communications* 23 (2024): 2003–2023.
31. A. Manchare, S. Parit, M. Lele, and N. Hatvate, “Exploring the Therapeutic Potential of 1,3-Thiazole: A Decade Overview,” *Medicinal Chemistry* 21 (2025): 1087–1104
32. A. M. Borcea, I. Ionuț, O. Crișan, and O. Oniga, “An Overview of the Synthesis and Antimicrobial, Antiprotozoal, and Antitumor Activity of Thiazole and Bisthiazole Derivatives,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)* 26(2021): 624.
33. Zoltewicz JA, Deady LW. Quaternization of heteroaromatic compounds: quantitative aspects. *Adv Heterocycl Chem.* 1978; 22:71–121.
34. Gabriel S. Synthese von oxazolen und thiazolen II. *European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry.* 1910; 43:1283-1287
35. Willstatter R, Wirth T. Uber Thioformamid. *Ber Dtsch Chem Ges.* 1909; 42:1908–1922.
36. George YS, Subhi AA. Preparation and spectral characterization of substituted 2-aminothiazoles. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data.* 1973;18(1):99-102
37. Ayman WE, Sherif MS, Hatem MG. The chemistry of α -haloketones and their utility in heterocyclic synthesis. *Molecules.* 2003;8(1):793-865
38. Uddin MK, Javed NM, Kumar A. Biological potential of benzoxazole derivatives: an updated review. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2020;13(8):15–28. doi:10.22159/ajpcr.2020.v13i8.37958.
39. Chhabria MT, Patel S, Modi P, Brahm kshatriya PS. Thiazole: a review on chemistry, synthesis and therapeutic importance. *Curr Top Med Chem.* 2016;16(26):2841–2862. doi:10.2174/1568026616666160506130741.
40. El-Gohary NS, Shaaban MI. Synthesis and biological evaluation of benzoxazole derivatives. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2017; 127:700–718. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2016.10.046.
41. Baumann M, Baxendale IR. An overview of the synthetic routes to thiazoles. *Beilstein J Org Chem.* 2013; 9:2265–2319. doi:10.3762/bjoc.9.265.
42. Cremer D, Kraka E. Chemical bonds and reactivity of heteroaromatic compounds. *J Am Chem Soc.* 1985;107(12):3800–3810. doi:10.1021/ja00298a015.
43. Kamal UD, Javed NM, Arun KU. Biological potential of benzoxazole derivatives: an updated review. *Asian J. Pharm. Clin. Res.* 2020;13(8):28-41.
44. Kumar A, Pal V, Mishra DK. Benzoxazole: Synthetic Methodology and Biological Activities. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research.* 2025;85(2).
45. Ai Chaoui H, Guenadil F, Kapanda CN, Lambert DM, McCurdy CR, Poupart JH. Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of antioxidant chalcone derivatives of 2(3H)-benzoxazolone. *Med Chem Res.* 2009; 18:467–476.
46. Garre Palli S, Kumar MP, Sai AP, Sharanya B, Mai GJ, Abhinav Gandhi C, et al. Synthesis and biological evaluation of benzoxazole derivatives as new anti-inflammatory agents. *Int J BioPharma.* 2012;3(1):50–54.
47. Sondhi MS, Singh N, Kumar A, Lozach A, Meijer L. Synthesis, anti-inflammatory, analgesic and kinase (CDK1, CDK-5 and GSK-3) inhibition activity evaluation of benzimidazole/benzoxazole derivatives and

- some Schiff's bases. *Bioorg Med Chem.* 2006; 14:3758–3765.
48. Unlu S, Baytas SN, Kupeli E, Yesilada E. Studies on novel 7-acyl-5-chloro-2-oxo-3H-benzoxazole derivatives as potential analgesic and anti-inflammatory agents. *Arch Pharm.* 2003; 336:310–21.
49. Aggarwal N, Kaur A, Anand K, Kumar H, Wakode SR. Biologically active Benzoxazole: A comprehensive review. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.* 2017;2(2):1-5.
50. Hunt JA, Gonzalez S, Kallashi F, Hammond ML, Pivnichny JV, Tong X, et al. 2-Arylbenzoxazoles as CETP inhibitors: substitution and modification of the α -alkoxyamide moiety. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett.* 2010; 20:1019–1022.
51. Koksall M, Gokhan N, Kupeli E, Yesilada E, Erdogan H. Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities of some new Mannich bases of 5-nitro-2-benzoxazolinones. *Arch Pharm Res.* 2007; 30:419–424.
52. Kim BJ, Kim J, Kim YK, Choi SY, Choo HYP. Synthesis of benzoxazole amides as novel antifungal agents against *Malassezia furfur*. *Bull Korean Chem Soc.* 2010;31(5):1217–1222.
53. Laeeq SH, Sirbaiya AK, Siddiqui HH. Benzoxazole: progress report on chemistry, synthesis and biological activities. *Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research.* 2013;3(12):8550-62.
54. Praveena C, Nandakumar A, Dheenkumar P, Muralidharan D, Perumal PT. Microwave-assisted one-pot synthesis of benzothiazole and benzoxazole libraries as analgesic agents. *J Chem Sci.* 2012; 124:609–624.
55. Desai PS, Desai HR. *J Indian Chem Soc.* 1994;71:155–157.
56. Vinsova J, Horak V, Buchta V, Kaustova J. *Molecules.* 2005; 10:783–793.
57. Kouatly O, Geronikaki A, Kamoutsis C, Hadjipavlou-Litina D, Eleftheriou P. Adamantane derivatives of thiazolyl-N-substituted amide as possible non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2009; 44:1198-1204.
58. He LY, Zhang SS, Peng DX, Guan LP, Wang SH. Synthesis and evaluations of selective COX-2 inhibitory effects: benzo[d]thiazol analogs. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett.* 2020;30(17):127376. doi: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2020.127376.
59. Soliman S, Soliman A, Alzoubar K, Merza J, Alasmi A. Systematic Review on Thiazole Compounds as Nanoparticles: Chemistry, Synthesis, Antimicrobial Activities, Therapeutic Investigation. *Nanomaterial, Nanotechnology.* 2023 Jan 1;21(1).
60. Sahiba N, Sethiya A, Soni J, Agarwal DK, Agarwal S. Saturated five-membered thiazolidines and their derivatives: from synthesis to biological applications. *Top Curr Chem.* 2020;378(2):34. doi:10.1007/s41061-020-0298-4.
61. Chawla A, Kaur H, Chawla P, Baghel US. A review on chemistry and biological activities of thiazole derivatives. *J Global Trends Pharma Sci.* 2014;5(2):1641-8.
62. Kini S, Swain S, Gandhi A. Synthesis and evaluation of novel benzothiazole derivatives against human cervical cancer cell lines. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2007;69(1):46–50.
63. Chandrappa S, Kavitha CV, Shahabuddin MS, Vinaya K, Anandakumar CS, Ranganatha SR, Raghavan SC, Rang Appa KS. Chemistry and biological activities of thiazole derivatives. *Bioorg Med Chem.* 2009; 17:2576–2584.
64. Youssef MSK, Ahmed RA, Abbady MS, AbdelMohsen SA, Omar AA. Chemistry and biological activities of thiazole derivatives. *Monatsh Chem.* 2008; 139:553–559.

65. Gupta V, Kant V. A review on biological activity of imidazole and thiazole moieties and their derivatives. *Sci. Int.* 2013 Jul 1;1(7):253-60.
66. Chandrappa S, Kavitha CV, Shahabuddin MS, et al. Synthesis and biological evaluation of benzoxazole derivatives as anticancer agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry.* 2009;17(7):2576–2584.
67. Alam O, Khan SA, Siddiqui N, Ahsan W, Verma SP, Gilani SJ. Review on thiazole derivatives: synthesis and biological activities. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry.* 2010;45(11):5113–5123.

HOW TO CITE: Nitika, Dr. Chinu Kumari, Dr. Abhishek Soni, Bhopesh Kumar, Yushmita Thakur, Riya Verma, Saurabh Rana, A Review on the Physicochemical and Biological Properties of Benzoxazole and Thiazole Derivatives, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 2771-2789. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20151500>

